

Indian Ocean:A Trade Route of Women Trafficking

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Abstract

Women trafficking is not a new phenomenon. Women trafficking became an established international industry. Women trafficking is the modern form of old slavery. Indian Ocean is the common path of women trafficking all over world. Women are trafficked for labour, begging, forcible marriages, for exploitation, to serve in sex industry, and to sell their body organs etc. The ship contains the millions of young girls through Indian ocean which are trafficked within Asia, Gulf and Europe. Women trafficking means it is nightmare in the dreamland. The south Asia, one of most growing regions of human trafficking. The major objectives are those factors which contributes towards women trafficking abroad. Apart from this to bring into limelight the magnitude of women trafficking in Indian ocean. Besides this is to prove that the human trafficking in women is human rights violation. Also suggest the counter –measure remedies include prevention, protection, and prosecution that how to stop this heinous crime. The qualitative and descriptive research methodology will be applied to this research paper. The socio-economic approach will be applied in this research paper to make an analysis. The data collection will take place through secondary resources i.e. Books, documentaries, news channels, journals, magazines, newspapers, survey reports and published interviews etc. at the end, the findings of research paper that from which countries mostly the women trafficking takes place through Indian ocean. Even the internal authorities are involved to support the women trafficking.

Keywords: women trafficking, An international industry, Indian ocean, gender –based violence.

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